

SOFT COMPOSITES FOR CHARGE TRANSPORT AND STORAGE TO SYNERGISTICALLY ENHANCE ENERGY HARVESTING PERFORMANCE OF TRIBOELECTRIC GENERATORS

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ABSTRACT

The incorporation of interlayers between the charge-generating layers and current collectors of triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) has been found as an effective strategy to significantly increase power output, indicating their critical role in charge retention. However, there is a lack of direct experimental evidence of charge distribution in the interlayers. We introduce herein a novel approach of self-bonding and de-stacking to quantitatively characterize volume charge distributions within the interlayers as well as the charge-generating layers. The total charge within each layer is determined by measuring their surface potential. Applying this method on multilayer TENGs composed of different materials shows that the charge-generating layer holds roughly the same amount of charge independent of the interlayer characteristics, while the interlayer can store electrical charges depending on its conductivity and dielectric constant. At an optimal balance between these properties, a 220% increase in electrical output has been found compared to conventional TENGs without interlayers and a 50% increase over those with only one interlayer.

1 INTRODUCTION

Triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) have emerged as a promising technology, which are operated through the coupling effects of triboelectrification and electrostatic induction. It offers several advantages, including large range of material selection, lightweight, low-cost, high-power output, making them highly adaptable for diverse applications. Several studies have shown good potential of integrating TENGs into medical and therapeutic application [1-3]. However, the development of triboelectric materials with high power output performance are crucial to power medical devices. Various methods have been previously explored to enhance the performance of TENG by improving permittivity of composite materials, performing surface engineering [4, 5] and so on. The above methods have contributed significantly to improving the output performance of the TENGs.

However, the performance of TENGs is largely influenced by the surface charge density of the triboelectric material.[6] Unfortunately, surface charges tend to decay quickly due to factors such as air breakdown, ambient humidity and charge diffusion which can significantly reduce the output.[7] Delaying the surface charge decay time is particularly important to improve the output performance of TENGs. Triboelectric charge drift or diffusion is one of major factor causing triboelectric charges decay.

During continuous operation of TENG, the negative triboelectric layer captures negative triboelectric charges from the positive triboelectric layer, accumulating them on its surface. At the same time, the bottom electrode beneath the negative triboelectric layer generates induced positive charges via electrostatic induction establishing an upward electric field.[8] Consequently, triboelectric charge decay occurs through charge drift and diffusion. The drift is driven by the electric field, and the diffusion driven by the electron's concentration gradient.

To mitigate triboelectric charge dissipation in TENG, an effective strategy involves employing composite films that incorporate high-permittivity fillers within the triboelectric layer. For instance, Tantraviwat et al enhanced the dielectric constant by incorporating PDMS with $BaTiO_3$ which significantly boosted the output performance.[9] Furthermore, conductive fillers have also been incorporated into composites because of its great charge storage capacity to enable charge transport deeper within the film and boost performance.[10] For example, Sun et al. used a conductive MWCNT network in TPU film, significantly enhancing output current by dispersing surface charges into the TPU layer's interior.[11]

Another effective strategy to reduce charge diffusion and drift involves embedding an intermediate layer between the triboelectric layer and electrode, which can transport, storage and block charges. High-permittivity materials such as TiO_2 [12, 13] and BTO [14] have been developed as charge-blocking layers to enhance TENG output. For example, Park et al. showed that incorporating a TiO_x electron-blocking layer with high permittivity enhanced TENG output power by 25 times, owing to its combined electron-blocking and polarization effects [13]. Similarly, Wu et al. introduced a SiO_2 layer to trap charges on hydrophobic fluoropolymer surfaces, leading to the development of a novel charge-trapping nanogenerator[15]. Furthermore, Jiang et al. demonstrated that placing a charge-trapping-blocking intermediate layer composed of rGO and Ag nanoparticles between the triboelectric layer and the electrode can significantly boost the output performance.[16]

Although interlayers have been shown to be effectively enhanced the power outputs of TENGs, direct experimental evidence regarding how the charges are distributed beneath the surface of the charge generating layer remains limited. This leaves a significant gap in understanding the volume charge distributions within the interior of various interlayer types, such as transporting layer,[11] storage layer,[16] and blocking layer.

In this study, we present a novel approach for quantifying the electrical charge distribution beneath the charge-generating surface using a stacking and de-stacking technique. To investigate the influence of dielectric constant and conductivity on charge distribution, we developed a composite tri-layer TENG comprising a PDMS-based charge generating layer, a charge-transporting layer (PDMS nanocomposite with multi-wall carbon nanotube MWCNT) and a charge-storage layer (PDMS nanocomposite with $BaTiO_3$). By adjusting the concentrations of nanofillers, we tuned the electrical conductivity and dielectric constant of the interlayers to determine the optimal combination for maximizing output performance. Enabled by a commercially scalable fabrication process, the composite tri-layer TENG holds strong potential for advancing high performance, self-powered wearable and implantable medical devices.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 provides a schematic overview of the multilayer composite TENG device structure including intermediate layers. In this configuration, a thin PDMS film acts as the negative triboelectric

layer, while the bottom aluminum film serves as the electrode. The top aluminum film functions both as the positive triboelectric layer and as an additional electrode. To enhance performance of the TENG, intermediate layers were introduced between the PDMS and aluminum electrode. An MWCNT/PDMS hybrid layer was incorporated as a charge transport layer, while a BaTiO₃/PDMS hybrid layer served as a charge-storage layer. As illustrated in **Figure 1a-c**, three designs were developed: Design A, consisting of a pristine PDMS thin layer; Design B, featuring a PDMS layer with a BaTiO₃/PDMS hybrid layer inserted between the PDMS and the aluminum electrode; and Design C, which included both an MWCNT/PDMS hybrid layer and a BaTiO₃/PDMS hybrid layer inserted between the PDMS and the aluminum electrode.

Figure 1: Multilayer TENG Configurations. a) Design A features a single PDMS layer. b) Design B includes one intermediate BaTiO₃/PDMS layer as charge-storage layer. c) Design C incorporates two intermediate layers: MWCNT/PDMS as charge-transporting layer and BaTiO₃/PDMS as charge-storage layer.

2.1 ELECTRICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF DIFFERENT MULTILAYER COMPOSITE TENGs

Based on the prepared composite films, the electrical output performance of samples was tested in the vertical contact-separation mode during the experiment. **Figure 2a** demonstrated the working principle of the multilayer composite TENG. The electricity generation cycle is governed by the combined effects of contact electrification and electrostatic induction. When the aluminium film contacts the PDMS surface, electrons transfer between the two-contacting surface due to their different electron affinities (**Figure 2a(i)**). As the aluminium film moves away from the PDMS, a potential difference is established, driving electrons through the external circuit from the top electrode to the bottom one (**Figure 2a(ii)**). This current continues until an equilibrium is reached at the point of maximum separation (**Figure 2a(iii)**). When the aluminium film returns toward the PDMS surface, the process reverses: electrons flow from the bottom to the top electrode (**Figure 2a(iv)**). Through repeated contact and separation, the multilayer composite TENG generates alternating current (AC) electricity,

which can be rectified and stored in a battery or capacitor to power electronic devices. During this cycle, electric charges also flow through the PDMS and the charge-transporting layer (**Figure 2a(ii)**), driven by the internal electric field. This charge flow continues from the generation surface to the storage layer until a new equilibrium is reached.

Figure 2b-d plots the output performance of different multilayer composite TENGs working at the frequency of 2 Hz. The pristine TENG without the additional layer shows a peak open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 243 V, peak short-circuit current (I_{sc}) of 1.2 μA and transferred charge (Q_{sc}) of 33 nC. Later, Design B with a BaTiO₃/PDMS hybrid layer exhibits enhanced output, with the V_{oc} , I_{sc} and Q_{sc} of 575 V, 3 μA and 54 nC respectively. Design C with the MWCNT/PDMS and BaTiO₃/PDMS hybrid layers demonstrate further enhancement in output performance with V_{oc} of ~ 1103 V, I_{sc} of 6.18 μA and Q_{sc} of 73 nC respectively. Accordingly, the enhancement of the output I_{sc} with the MWCNT/PDMS and BaTiO₃/PDMS hybrid layers is almost 5 times that of the pristine TENG.

Figure 2: Electrical Characterization of different multilayer composite TENGs. a) Working mechanism of the tri-layer TENG. b) V_{oc} of TENGs. c) I_{sc} of TENGs. d) Q_{sc} of TENGs.

As electrons accumulate on the contact surface, they induce positive charges on the bottom electrode, forming a vertically upward built-in electric field between the surface and the electrode. This field initiates two modes of electron transport: drift which is driven by the electric field, and diffusion which is caused by the concentration gradient of electrons. Both mechanisms can lead to the recombination of triboelectric electrons with the induced positive charges on the electrode, resulting in charge loss. Moreover, triboelectric electrons may also recombine with adsorbed positively charged ions or air particles, further contributing to the performance degradation observed in conventional TENGs.^[17]

To overcome these limitations, we incorporate a charge transport layer and a charge storage layer between the triboelectric layer and the bottom electrode. The charge transport layer provides a conductive pathway, enabling efficient migration of triboelectric charges away from the surface. This mitigates repulsive interactions with incoming charges, thereby improving charge accumulation efficiency.[11] The charge storage layer, characterized by strong electron-trapping capability, suppresses recombination between electrons and induced positive charges.[13] Additionally, embedding high-permittivity fillers into these layers enhances the overall dielectric constant, further boosting the output performance of the composite tri-layer TENG.[9]

To evaluate the charge accumulation performance of three multilayer composite TENGs, a series of contact-separation tests were conducted using a linear motor with a 1 mm displacement, 100 N contact force, and 2 Hz frequency. The electrical performance of three test samples was compared. The corresponding open-circuit voltage and maximum charge transfer density for each design are presented in **Figure 3a-b**. Design A showed a moderate voltage increase from 97 V to 243 V. Design B demonstrated greater improvement, with V_{oc} rising from 230 V to 575 V, attributed to the enhanced permittivity and electron-trapping capability of the BaTiO₃/PDMS layer.[18] In Design C, the incorporation of a conductive intermediate layer with the MWCNT/PDMS transport layer enable an V_{oc} of 238 V and then eventually saturating at 1103 V. The sharp rise in voltage suggests effective charge storage within the composite tri-layer TENG. Design C reached a maximum charge transfer density of 3.3 nC/cm², which is 3 times compared with that of Design A, which did not include intermediate layers. This improvement is primarily attributed to the charge transport layer, which facilitates the movement of triboelectric charges away from the surface. By alleviating charge repulsion during subsequent cycles, it significantly boosts the device's overall performance.

Figure 3: Charge accumulation of multilayer composite TENGs. a) V_{oc} (open circuit current). b) Q_{sc} (transferred charge density). c) after-contact surface potential of different designs. d) Surface potential decay of different designs.

2.2 SURFACE POTENTIAL CHARACTERIZATION FOR DIFFERENT MULTILAYER COMPOSITE TENGs

The origin of surface charge is a fundamental aspect of TENG, essential for visualizing and quantifying the creation and dissipation processes of triboelectric charges during contact and separation movements[19]. To better understand this, we systematically investigated the performance of Designs A, B, and C using surface potential measurements, with the aim of confirming the advantages of the MWCNT/PDMS charge-transporting layer and the BaTiO₃/PDMS charge-storage layer. Any residual charges on the surface of each test layer were neutralized before measurement to ensure a zero-surface potential which is verified by the electrostatic voltmeter. The surface potential was then measured at 3 mm to accurately assess the charge characteristics on the nanocomposite surface. These measurements were performed after driving the TENG samples using a linear motor operating at a frequency of 2 Hz and a force of 100 N.

As shown in **Figure 3c**, the surface potential trends are similar with those of the V_{oc} across all designs, with potential values increasing as the tapping time rose. This correlation indicates that the surface potential is directly tied to the contact-separation numbers. For Design A, the surface potential stabilized around -300 V after 50 s tapping time, indicating a limitation in net charge accumulation due to contact electrification. In comparison, the surface potential of Design B continued to rise after 25 s of tapping, eventually stabilizing at approximately -700 V after 100 s. This enhancement is contributed by the BaTiO₃/PDMS layer, whose high dielectric constant and strong electron-trapping ability effectively reduce electron recombination, thereby improving both charge retention and surface potential.^[9,20] As a result, the elevated surface charge enhanced electrostatic induction at both electrodes, leading to increases in V_{oc} , I_{sc} , and Q_{sc} . With the addition of an intermediate MWCNT/PDMS transporting layer, Design C exhibited a continuous rise in surface potential from approximately -870 V to -1160 V which is nearly four times compared with that of Design A. The charge transporting layer enables deeper migration of charges away from the surface, reducing electrostatic repulsion on incoming charges and promoting more efficient charge accumulation at the top interface. This improvement not only enhances the charge storage capacity but also increases the depth of charge retention within the triboelectric material.

To evaluate the charge-storage capabilities of the TENGs, surface potential decay was measured following 200 seconds of tapping. Due to an 18s delay between the linear motor halting and the positioning of the electrostatic voltmeter probe, surface potentials were estimated by extrapolating the measured data to time zero using a double-exponential fitting function: $V = Ae^{-\frac{x}{\tau}} + Be^{-\frac{x}{\tau}}$, as shown in **Figure 3d**. The extrapolated surface potentials after 200 s of tapping were approximately -300 V, -700 V, and -1160 V for Designs A, B, and C, respectively. Designs B and C exhibited prolonged surface potential retention compared to Design A, with Design C maintaining a measurable potential for over 8 minutes after continuous contact cycles. Design A experienced a more rapid decay, whereas Designs B and C displayed nearly identical and slower decay rates. These findings confirm that the integration of MWCNT/PDMS and BaTiO₃/PDMS interlayers play a crucial role in stabilizing and enhancing the

output performance of the TENG.

To further investigate the charge distribution the mechanisms contributing to the enhanced output performance and particularly the effects of the conductive filler (MWCNT) and the high-permittivity filler (BaTiO_3), we conducted additional experiments to examine the surface potential of each individual layer in Designs A, B, and C.

As illustrated in **Figures 4**, each design was fabricated layer-by-layer. Design A served as the baseline and did not contain any fillers. Design B incorporated a layer-by-layer assembly with a pure PDMS triboelectric layer and an additional layer containing the dielectric filler BaTiO_3 . Design C included a triboelectric layer, a charge-transporting layer, and a charge-storage layer. To ensure consistent testing, a linear motor was employed to ensure 200s tapping time at 2 Hz frequency and 100 N force for all three designs. Furthermore, we measured the surface potential layer by layer using a peeling method which allowed for a precise assessment of each layer's contribution to the overall charge distribution. Surface potentials for the layers were measured using an electrostatic voltmeter setup as presented in **Figure 4b**, where the measurement probe was set at 3 mm above a separated PDMS layer that was placed on the ground plane. The probe of an electrostatic voltmeter detects the electric field and measures voltage relative to the ground plane on which the dielectric layer is placed.

Surface potential measurements were conducted layer by layer using a peeling method, as illustrated in **Figure 4a**, enabling precise evaluation of each layer's contribution to the overall charge distribution. As shown in **Figure 4c**, Design C exhibited the highest total surface potential among the three configurations. The surface potentials of the PDMS charge-generating layers in Design B (~334 V) and Design C (~350 V) were slightly higher than that in Design A (~300 V), suggesting that the interlayers contributed to the increased potential in Design C. The charge-transporting layer in Design C showed a relatively low surface potential (~200 V), indicating its limited charge retention capacity due to high conductivity which an attribute that facilitates efficient charge transfer to deeper layers. Notably, the surface potential of the charge-storage layer in Design C was significantly higher than in Design B, confirming that the addition of a charge-transporting layer between the PDMS and BaTiO_3 /PDMS layers enhanced charge transfer and accumulation, thereby improving the surface potential of the charge-storage layer.

Based on the measured surface potentials, the volume charge density can be determined using Gauss's law. For a single dielectric layer with cross-sectional area S and thickness d , placed on a grounded plane at $z = 0$, the total enclosed charge between z and $z = d$ can be expressed in terms of the volume charge density ρ

$$Q_{enclosed} = S \int_z^d \rho dz = S\rho(d - z) \quad [1]$$

The electric displacement field D at a distance z above the ground plane can be expressed as:

$$D = \frac{Q_{enclosed}}{S} = \rho(d - z) \quad [2]$$

The resulting electric field within the dielectric material is:

$$E(z) = \frac{D(z)}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r} = \frac{\rho(d-z)}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r} \quad [3]$$

where ϵ_0 represents the permittivity of air, ϵ_r is the relative permittivity of the dielectric material.

The surface potential at the top surface ($z = d$) is determined by integrating the electric field from a position z up to d :

$$V(d) = -\int_z^d Edz = -\frac{d^2 - \frac{1}{2}d^2}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r} = -\frac{\rho d^2}{2\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r} \quad [4]$$

Using Equation [4], the volume charge densities of the three individual layers in the tri-layer PDMS stack were calculated to be 920.634 nC/cm³, 501.816 nC/cm³, and 648.587 nC/cm³, as depicted in **Figure 4d**. These values highlight the variation in charge distribution across the different material layers.

Figure 4: Surface potential measurement and volume charge density analysis in multilayer TENG with composite materials. a) Schematic representation of the surface potential measurement procedure for different TENG design layers. b) Illustration depicting the steps involved in surface potential measurement. c) Experimental results showing the measured surface potential across layers in various TENG configurations. d) Trend of volume charge density within the multilayer composite stack.

The relationship between TENG output and external resistance under a 2 Hz excitation frequency and 100 N contact force is shown in **Figure 5**. As expected by Ohm's law, the output voltage increased with external resistance, while the current correspondingly decreased. The peak power density of the composite tri-layer TENG was observed across varying load resistances, reaching a maximum of 1.22 W/m² at 300 MΩ. This level of output is sufficient to power many wireless wearable and implantable medical devices, highlighting the strong potential of the composite tri-layer TENG. Nevertheless, extending the operational lifespan of wearable and implantable medical devices will

require not only efficient power generation but also optimized power management systems and reduced device power consumption.

Figure 5: Effect of external load resistance on the output characteristics of the TENG, showing the variations in voltage, current, and power density.

3 CONCLUSIONS

This study introduces a novel approach for measuring and understanding charge distribution beneath the friction surface, utilizing a tri-layered composite TENG stack design. By examining the individual layers of this stack, we quantified the charge distributions within the individual layers of the TENG. These results were achieved through in-depth investigation of the enhancement mechanisms, including physical characterizations and detailed electrical measurements. For the first time, we visualized the surface potential of layers beneath the triboelectric layer, shedding light on charge distribution below the surface and confirming the effectiveness of the MWCNT/PDMS charge-transporting layer and the BaTiO₃/PDMS charge-storage layer using surface potential measurements.

Based on these findings, a high-performance tri-layered composite TENG was developed featuring a structural design that incorporates intermediate layers. These layers are composed of MWCNT/PDMS and BaTiO₃/PDMS hybrid films, serving as the charge-transporting layer and charge-storage layer respectively. This combination enabled electrical charges to be stored in the dielectric component without affecting the charges in the generating layer, significantly increasing the TENG's transferred charge density to 3.3 nC/cm² and a maximum power density of 1.2 W/m². The new tri-layered composite TENG demonstrates significant potential for integration into self-powered medical devices. Future research will focus on optimizing the materials and device architecture to enhance durability, efficiency, and pave the way for broader adoption in medical and consumer electronics.

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